

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
1	D1.8	D8	Matchmaking event report	UT

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	D7 (D1.7) D23 (D4.3)

Description (short)
This document provides an overview of the matchmaking event organized by the ENLIGHT alliance and summarises its results (participant numbers, participant feedback, usage of the b2match platform).

Document Version Control		
Version 0.1	Originated by:	UT
Version 0.2	Originated by:	UT after WP1 members' comments and edits
Final version	Originated by:	UT after PB members' comments and edits
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15585511	

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

Introduction	3
Date and format	4
Event sessions and participation	4
B2match platform integration	6
Participant feedback	8
Conclusions	8
Appendix 1 – FINAL ENLIGHT matchmaking event programme	9
Appendix 2 – Feedback overview	11

Introduction

ENLIGHT is a European University formed by ten comprehensive research-intensive universities from ten European countries¹ (University of the Basque Country in Spain, University of Bern in Switzerland, University of Bordeaux in France, Comenius University Bratislava in Slovakia, University of Galway in Ireland, Ghent University in Belgium, University of Göttingen in Germany, University of Groningen in the Netherlands, University of Tartu in Estonia, Uppsala University in Sweden).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

One of the key aims of the ENLIGHT RISE project is to promote cooperation between alliance researchers. In December 2023, an amendment to shift from the development of the digital matching tool for ENLIGHT researchers to the organization of the matchmaking event was approved by the EC, changing the content of this deliverable from the report on the pilot implementation of the digital matching tool to the report on the matchmaking event. The ENLIGHT Matchmaking Event took place on April 29, 2024. The day saw sessions that allowed ENLIGHT researchers to present their ideas for building joint projects, promoted future opportunities for researcher collaboration within ENLIGHT 2.0 and presented tools developed within RISE that can interest ENLIGHT researchers. The event was supported by a dedicated b2match page, which has remained available after the event. On April 30, a co-scheduled WP4 event for early career researchers took place to promote synergies and improve visibility of the RISE activities.

The event on April 29 served as a link and transition between the ENLIGHT RISE (Horizon2020 SwafS) and ENLIGHT 2.0 (Erasmus+) projects, as we used the event to promote ENLIGHT 2.0 instruments, attracted participants from the University of Bern and organized a pitching session for the Culture and Creativity focus area.² We believe the event also helped us strengthen the overall position of research within the alliance, which is particularly important in a situation where the research and innovation side of the alliance will no longer have dedicated funding. In what follows, we describe the event in more detail and give an overview of the received feedback as well as consider the usefulness of organizing similar events in the future.

¹ ENLIGHT has expanded to formally include the University of Bern with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0.

² This is a new focus area for the alliance added with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0.

Date and format

As explained in D1.7, although we initially planned to organize an in-person matchmaking event in Tartu, we eventually opted for an online event. This was due to several reasons, including dates that were suitable for most partners; longer than expected internal negotiations on the amendment, and therefore a relatively short timeframe for practical arrangements; challenges with venues and accommodation due to Tartu being European Cultural Capital this year, and environmental considerations.

While we recognize that online events are not a substitute for in-person interaction,³ in hindsight we can conclude that organizing an online event was the best possible format to achieve our objective of reaching and connecting a large number of researchers. The event proved to be a success with 224 registrations on the platform and 199 participants joining the various sessions on April 29 (based on the Zoom report). This means we managed to attract more than three times more participants than we would have been able to do had we organized a physical event – we estimated that we could bring around 60 participants to Tartu.

Event sessions and participation

The matchmaking event started with an opening session with several presentations about ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT 2.0. Firstly, we provided an overview of the ENLIGHT alliance, its focus, and achievements to date, as well as briefly introduced ENLIGHT 2.0. We then moved to present the upcoming opportunities and (recently opened) calls for researchers and academics in ENLIGHT 2.0, such as ENLIGHT Incubator Grants, ENLIGHT Thematic Networks, ENLIGHT+⁴ and ENLIGHT AIM Days. Finally, we introduced the pitching sessions that followed and the matchmaking platform⁵ (see below). The session was attended by ≈ 76 people.⁶

The session above was followed by pitching sessions for setting up research collaborations within ENLIGHT. Researchers who were looking for partners to establish an ENLIGHT Thematic Network, submit a joint funding proposal or start a joint project pitched their ideas to other ENLIGHT researchers. We originally scheduled two parallel pitching sessions, one after another, with three breakout rooms per ENLIGHT challenge area in each. Each of the six sessions had two ENLIGHT RISE R&I Support Group/WP1 members assigned to moderate them, with one other member or UT staff serving as

³ Indeed in one feedback form it was suggested that “Such event should be also proposed physically and as everybody know the main interest of an event is the off discussion during break!”

⁴ <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/university-about-us/news-events/158-news/1095-prepare-calls-2024>.

⁵ <https://www.b2match.com/e/enlight-rise>.

⁶ Naturally, people were joining and leaving sessions, hence \approx symbol.

backup in case of technical issues. However, due to last minute cancellations as well as new requests from researchers some changes to the agenda were necessary.

Firstly, we received a request to organize a special meeting on hydrogen topics, which was scheduled during the time of the first parallel pitching session to avoid an overlap with the Energy and Circular Economy breakout room that was scheduled in the next session. This was done to ensure that interested researchers could attend both. Secondly, there were cancellations of pitches in the challenge area Equity and Energy and Circular Economy. As a result, there were no pitchers left in Equity, and only one pitch on hydrogen left in Energy and Circular Economy.

After discussing the situation among the organizers and respective moderators, we concluded that having a session with no pitches to steer the discussion may be suboptimal and would require really good moderators' skills. In parallel, we consulted the researcher with interest in hydrogen who originally registered for Energy and Circular Economy. Furthermore, due to personal reasons, one assigned moderator had to cancel at the last moment, which also required action on our part. To accommodate all these circumstances, we:

1. Canceled a separate session on equity and redirected interested participants to the session on Culture and Creativity.
2. Canceled a separate session on Energy and Circular Economy. One remaining pitcher with a hydrogen topic accepted an invitation and participated in the special hydrogen meeting. Other interested participants were also redirected to either the hydrogen session or climate change session depending in their interests.
3. Reassigned moderators adding more backup to each session to ensure that April 29 will not see major interruptions due to unexpected circumstances.

As a result, parallel session one included Health and Wellbeing, Culture and Creativity (with an option for researchers interested in Equity to join), Climate Change (with an option for researchers interested in Energy and Circular Economy to join) and an additional session on hydrogen. Session two included Digitalization and Digital Revolution (see Annex 1 for updated program). While we asked presenters to send in their pitches in advance to prepare slides decks per session, we also left room for spontaneous pitches in case a session had enough time. Generally, pitches were expected to be up to 5 minutes, based on the provided pitching slides template, followed by 5 minutes of questions from the audience. The table below summarizes participation in the various pitching sessions:

Topic	# of pitches	# of participants
Health and Wellbeing	8	≈ 39
Culture and Creativity (+Equity)	4	≈ 25
Climate Change (+Energy and Circular Economy)	9	≈ 14
Hydrogen meeting	1	≈ 11
Digitalization and Digital Revolution	3 + 1 from audience without pitching slides	≈ 34

According to moderators' reports, most sessions had lively discussions with active interest from participants. Most pitches were followed by at least a couple of questions from the audience, in many cases interest to keep in touch for future collaborations was expressed, with exchange of emails also taking place in the chat. We are aware of at least one ENLIGHT Thematic Network application on hydrogen that is being prepared as a result of the event.

The final session on April 29 was dedicated to the selected tools that we have developed in RISE that can be of use to ENLIGHT researchers. This included the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory,⁷ which can be used to find potential collaboration partners within ENLIGHT; ENLIGHT Impact Repository⁸ and ENLIGHT Open Science toolkit.⁹ We also reminded our researchers about the support officers' network that can be used for finding partners for joint projects, as well as remaining travel awards for partner visits. The session was attended by ≈ 55 people.

While the event on April 29 was open to all interested researchers, the April 30 programme focused on early career researchers (ECRs) in collaboration with WP4. This event represented the 3rd networking event for ECRs with a focus on leadership skills. Details of the event are provided in D4.3.

B2match platform integration

As mentioned above, the matchmaking event was supported by the dedicated [b2match platform](#). The platform served the purpose of participant registration for the April 29 event and contained links to join the various sessions. The image below is a screenshot taken on the day of the matchmaking event showing the number of people registered on the platform (total 224).

⁷ <https://observatory.enlight-eu.org/>.

⁸ <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/>.

⁹ <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/landing-research-and-innovation/open-science/1016-enlight-open-science-toolkit>.

Ireland	24		
Sweden	12		
Switzerland	9		
Belgium	9		
Germany	7		

Since the event, the number of people registered has slightly increased (228 registrations in total, 188 researchers and 40 R&I support)¹⁰ with the following distribution per mentioned challenge area:

Category	# of registrations
Health and wellbeing	118
Digital Revolution and impact of digitalization	75
Climate Change	56
Energy and Circular Economy	43
Culture and Creativity	42
Equity	40

The platform includes a number of functionalities for registered participants. It allows them to set up one-on-one meetings to discuss potential collaboration in detail. Furthermore, the platform has a [dedicated section](#) for posting various funding opportunities relevant to the ENLIGHT challenge areas (by R&I support staff) and collaboration offers/requests by partners. The table below summarizes the activities that have been carried out on the platform to date. The platform will remain operational until the end of January 2025. This will allow for continuous engagement of our researchers.

Type of action	How many times it has been taken
Messages sent	258
1:1 meetings	8
Posted collaboration opportunities	20
Posted funding opportunities	30

¹⁰ The numbers in this section are provided as of the date of deliverable writing, Jun 3, 2024.

Participant feedback

After the event, we sent out a feedback form to participants via the platform to evaluate the usefulness of the event and assess if there could be interest in similar events in the future. We received 18 responses to the feedback questionnaire which includes 11 questions on the satisfaction with and usefulness of the matchmaking event, its different sessions and the matchmaking platform (see Annex 2 for details).

Out of all the respondents, 77%¹¹ expressed overall satisfaction with the event as well as thought that similar events could be useful in the future. 71% of the respondents said that the opening session dedicated to the ENLIGHT consortium and opportunities it offers to researchers was informative and useful, while the pitching sessions were deemed informative and useful by 65% of the respondents. Regarding the matchmaking platform, 88% of the respondents found it to be convenient and easy to use, while 66% believed that the matchmaking platform is useful for making connections with fellow ENLIGHT researchers.

Conclusions

Given the overall number of event participants, the positive impressions expressed by the moderators of the pitching sessions, speakers and other ENLIGHT RISE project participants, as well as generally positive feedback we received (event though we recognize the small sample size), we consider the ENLIGHT Matchmaking event to be a success. The event clearly demonstrated that there is interest among the ENLIGHT researchers to connect and to pursue joint projects, which we hope will be taken into account as the alliance continues to develop. We also believe that similar events would be useful in the future, online or in-person, to solidify this trend. One opportunity that has already been discussed is to use the b2match platform and organize a similar event before the next round of ENLIGHT Thematic Networks applications, which is expected in spring 2025. Another opportunity that is being explored right now is the use of the platform to support the development of the ENLIGHT Community Challenge database. We will continue to explore these options in the near future.

¹¹ The presented % are sums of strongly and somewhat agree responses.

Appendix 1 – FINAL ENLIGHT matchmaking event programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

ENLIGHT Matchmaking Events

Monday, April 29, 2024 – ENLIGHT Tools and Pitching Sessions for Joint Applications and Projects

09:00-10:00 CET Welcome and opening (*plenary session*)

- Welcome from the University of Tartu Vice-Rector for Research Prof Mari Moora
- Overview of ENLIGHT: consortium, achievements, ENLIGHT 2.0
- Opportunities for researchers within ENLIGHT
- Intro of the pitching sessions and matchmaking platform

10:00-10:30 CET Break

10:30-12:00 CET Parallel pitching sessions per ENLIGHT focus area:

- Health and wellbeing
- Culture and creativity; Equity (*UPDATED*)
- Climate change; Energy and circular economy (*UPDATED*)
- Hydrogen Research Session (*ADDED*)

12:00-13:00 CET Break

13:00-14:30 CET Parallel pitching sessions per ENLIGHT focus area:

- Digitalization and digital revolution
- Equity (*CANCELED*)
- Energy and circular economy (*CANCELED*)

14:30-15:00 CET Break

15:00-16:00 CET ENLIGHT RISE tools and summary of the day (*plenary session*)

- R&I Observatory
- Open Science toolkit
- Impact tools
- Wrap-up

Tuesday, April 30, 2024 – Leadership Training and Networking for Early Career Researchers

10:00-11:00 CET Session I of leadership training and networking for ECRs

11:00-11:30 CET Break

11:30-12:30 CET Session II of leadership training and networking for ECRs

12:30-13:30 CET Lunch break

13:30-14:30 CET Session III of leadership training and networking for ECRs

Appendix 2 – Feedback overview

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	I did not attend this session
1. Overall, I am satisfied with the ENLIGHT matchmaking event that took place on Apr 29.	5 (27%) ¹²	9 (50%)		1 (5%)		3 (16%)
2. The opening session dedicated to the ENLIGHT consortium and opportunities it offers to researchers (ENLIGHT Thematic Networks, Incubator Grants etc.) was informative and useful.	8 (44%)	5 (27%)	1 (5%)			3 (16%)
3. How many pitching sessions did you attend?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 – 5 responses • 2 – 7 responses • More than 2 – 2 responses 					
4. The pitching session(s) I attended was (were) informative and useful.	5 (27%)	7 (38%)	1 (5%)		1 (5%)	1 (5%)
5. The closing session about ENLIGHT RISE tools (R&I Observatory, Open Science toolkit, impact tools) was informative and useful.	4 (22%)	4 (22%)	2 (11%)			5 (27%)
6. Overall, I have improved my understanding of ENLIGHT and its activities thanks to the matchmaking event.	7 (38%)	5 (27%)	2 (11%)			
7. Thanks to the event, I have identified potential collaborators within ENLIGHT.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes – 12 responses (67%) • No – 2 responses (11%) • No answer – 4 (22%) 					
8. I think similar events would be useful in the future.	11 (61%)	3 (16%)				
9. The matchmaking platform (https://www.b2match.com/e/enlight-rise/) is convenient and easy to use.	7 (38%)	9 (50%)	1 (5%)			1 (5%)

¹² % are provided out of the total number of responses (18); not all responders replied to all questions.

10. The matchmaking platform is useful for making connections with fellow ENLIGHT researchers.	1 (5%)	11 (61%)	4 (22%)			
11. Thanks to the platform, I have identified potential collaborators within ENLIGHT.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes – 12 responses (67%) • No – 3 responses (17%) • No answer – 3 (17%) 					

Further feedback:

- “Such event should be also proposed physically and as everybody know the main interest of an event is the off discussion during break!”
- “The topics of the pitches were too broad to fit my research interests.”